

ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR
OPERAS AS AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES
SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Data Management Plan

DELIVERABLE 1.2

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ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR OPERAS AS AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

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Data Management Plan

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Delivery Slip

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Abstract

The OPERAS-PLUS Data Management Plan (DMP) provides information regarding the collection, management, and processing of data collected and/or produced during the project phase (1 September 2022 - 31 August 2025) and outlines measures to make this data FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable).

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Contents

Delivery Slip	2
Abstract	2
I. Introduction	4
II. Data Summary	4
III. FAIR Data	9
IV. Allocation of Resources	12
V. Data Security	12
VI. Ethical Aspects	12

I. Introduction

The OPERAS-PLUS Data Management Plan (DMP) provides information regarding the collection, management, and processing of data collected and/or produced during the project phase (1 September 2022 - 31 August 2025) and outlines measures to make this data FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable).

The DMP includes information on¹:

- the handling of research data during and after the end of the project
- what data will be collected, processed, and/or generated
- which methodology and standards will be applied
- whether data will be shared/made open access
- how data will be curated and preserved (including after the end of the project).

The OPERAS-PLUS DMP is based on the Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template (version 1.0, 05 May 2021). The DMP is envisioned to be a living document and, over the course of the project, the DMP will be updated if significant changes arise. All changes to the DMP will be noted in a “History of Changes” table to be included in the annex of all updated versions.

The OPERAS-PLUS DMP follows the definition of research data and research data management as outlined in the “Practical Guide to the International Alignment of Research Data Management - Extended Edition” of 2021 by Science Europe.²

The DMP takes GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) compliance and the minimum FAIR³ requirements into account.

II. Data Summary

OPERAS-PLUS collects and generates different types of data:

- project management data and internal communication data, which is collected and processed for the successful project coordination and management;
- communication channels data and personal data;
- research data, in particular textual data;
- service related data (metrics service, pathfinder service, PRISM service, translation service).

¹ In compliance with the Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template (version 1.0, 05 May 2021).

² Science Europe. “Practical Guide to the International Alignment of Research Data Management - Extended Edition”. 2021. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4915861>.

³ See more on the FAIR principles: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>.

Data category:	Project management data
Data type:	Textual (working documents, presentations, deliverable technical specifications)
Data format(s):	docx, .pdf, .pptx, .xls, .csv
Size:	1 G
GDPR issues:	No
Data collection purpose:	Managing and coordinating the project.

Data category:	Internal communication data
Data type:	Mailing lists details, chat log, authentication, meeting recording
Data format(s):	.txt, .csv, .pdf
Size:	1 G
GDPR issues:	As this data can often contain sensitive information, it will not be shared with third parties outside the OPERAS-PLUS consortium. The project coordinator is responsible for the secure storage of the project management data.
Data collection purpose:	Managing and coordinating the project.

Data category:	Communication channels data
Data type:	Device IDs, location, IP address, and software for the OPERAS-PLUS website and OPERAS-PLUS blog as a continuation of the previous projects OPERAS-D and OPERAS-P; e-mail addresses for the newsletter and press contacts
Data format(s):	.html, .pdf, .jpg, .png, .css, .csv
Size:	835 MB
GDPR issues:	Mail addresses are externally processed by MailChimp (compliant with GDPR regulations ⁴). OPERAS-PLUS uses third-party services such as Google Analytics and Matomo, hosted by Huma-Num.
Data collection purpose:	Community building, communication, advocacy, user tracking and measuring Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

⁴ See: <https://mailchimp.com/en/help/about-the-general-data-protection-regulation/>.

Data category:	Personal data
Data type:	Sociodemographic data (first name, surname, sex, place of birth, phone-number, email address, profession), usage data (logging data or self-reported behavior), user feedback (oral/written form, interview transcripts, survey responses), behavioral data (services usage patterns), user-insights (documents, reports)
Data format(s):	.txt, .csv, .json, .xml, .doc/docx, .pdf, .jpeg/jpg/jp2, .png, .wav, .mp3, .mp4
Size:	2 G
GDPR issues:	Informed consent will be collected from participants.
Data collection purpose:	To gather information and receive input for the community needs.

Data category:	Research data
Data type:	Textual (reports, position papers, survey analysis)
Data format(s):	.csv, .rtf, .pdf, .TIFF6.0 uncompressed, .doc/docx, .odt, .jpeg/jpg/jp2
Size:	2 G
GDPR issues:	Best practices for protecting participant data in user research will be followed. ⁵
Data collection purpose:	To increase awareness for OPERAS and to strengthen the landscape analysis.

⁵ See for example:

<https://www.eui.eu/documents/servicesadmin/deanofstudies/researchethics/guide-data-protection-research.pdf>.

Data category:	Service related data: Metrics
Data type:	Data is stored as Events, includes Number of Views, Downloads, Reads on an EPUB reader, Citations, Book Visits on Google Books, Tweets about the publication, Hypothesis Annotations, References to the Book on sites such as Wikipedia and Wordpress. Each event will contain the date it occurred, and be saved against the primary identifier of the work the event relates to (this is usually a DOI). Certain events will also contain references, if available. Citation events will store the DOI of the publication that cited the work, Tweet Events will store the URL of the tweet mentioning the publication. Hypothesis Annotation events will store a link to the annotation in Hypothesis (public comments only). References to the publication on sites like wikipedia and wordpress will contain a link to the page that makes a reference to the publication. If available, the country that the event took place in is also stored. A description of each event measure is stored. Additionally, events that are deposited will be marked with an ID of the depository - usually their email address.
Data format(s):	Data is stored as rows in a PostgreSQL database.
Size:	Currently 13.8 GB (primarily metrics events)
GDPR issues:	Links to public hypothes.is annotations ⁶ and public tweets are stored, each of which might contain personal information (although that personal information is not stored in the OPERAS database).
Data collection purpose:	In order to deliver the OPERAS metrics service - i.e. so participating platforms can display aggregated metrics via the OPERAS metrics widget.

⁶ See for example: <https://hypothes.is/a/JLtdHBPNEedqJMHEqphsA>.

Data category:	Service related data: Pathfinder
Data type:	Relational database tables with data describing (editorial) services and service providers.
Data format(s):	Relational database tables (MariaDB)
Size:	With an estimation of 2,500 bytes per service and 3,000 bytes per service provider, also considering metadata, taxonomies, and support tables needed by the software framework used, we expect that the Pathfinder database won't exceed 20 megabytes by the end of 2023.
GDPR issues:	No
Data collection purpose:	Providing a comprehensive list of editorial services and service providers operating in the social sciences and humanities domain.

Data category:	Service related data: PRISM
Data type:	Textual (peer review information form)
Data format(s):	.doc/docx, .odt, .pdf
Size:	250 characters per peer review description; currently about 300 such descriptions in the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB). The total data size is estimated to stay well below 1 G.
GDPR issues:	No
Data collection purpose:	Provide information about a publisher's peer review process(es).

Data category:	Service related data: Translation
Data type:	Textual (reports, scientific papers)
Data format(s):	.doc/docx, .odt, .pdf
Size:	Variable - depends on the underlying file to be translated, an estimation of no more than 2 G over the course of the project OPERAS-PLUS.
GDPR issues:	To create a translated version of the original document.
Data collection purpose:	Provide information about a publisher's peer review process(es).

OPERAS-PLUS uses a Google Workspace, particularly a Google shared drive, to facilitate accessibility, co-writing and co-producing data. Files in a shared drive belong to the project team instead of individual members, ensuring accessibility and continuity even if individuals should leave their organization. Google Workspace uses various data centers⁷ and states to comply with legal frameworks⁸ when data is transferred outside of the European Economic Area (EEA). Google moreover states to be compliant with the European GDPR regulation.⁹ Mailing lists are archived and stored on a dedicated server at OpenEdition (France) and access to the mailing list archives is solely granted to mailing list subscribers.

No existing data will be re-used. The origin of the project management data as well as of the research data is from the project consortium. The data size will be a total of approx. 23,7 G.

The research data that the project generates will be useful first and foremost for the OPERAS research infrastructure and can in the future be re-used by researchers and other relevant stakeholders in the Social Sciences and Humanities.

III. FAIR Data

A. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

All OPERAS-PLUS outputs will receive persistent and unique identifiers as DOIs provided by Zenodo or other PIDs from relevant repositories, e.g. GitHub.

All OPERAS-PLUS publications are assigned to the Zenodo community “OPERAS: open scholarly communication in the European research area for social sciences and humanities”¹⁰. The project results will be uploaded to this Zenodo community rather than to a separate Zenodo community because the project’s results directly impact the research infrastructure.

The process on how to upload the documents and how to consistently add metadata is currently discussed within a dedicated task force (work packages 6 and 8). The results will be outlined in an OPERAS info sheet available at the Communication Toolbox.

⁷ See Google data centers location list: <https://www.google.com/about/datacenters/locations/>.

⁸ See: <https://policies.google.com/privacy/frameworks>.

⁹ See: <https://cloud.google.com/privacy/gdpr>.

¹⁰ See: <https://zenodo.org/communities/operaseu/?page=1&size=20>.

All contributors to data produced within OPERAS-PLUS have ORCID-IDs or are invited to create one.

OPERAS-PLUS will follow the naming standards for data files set in the OPERAS-P project to increase findability both within the project itself and across all OPERAS projects and initiatives. The file naming pattern is the following:

OPPLUS [WP number.Task number] - [producer] - [subject] - [version number] - [dissemination level].

Thereby, “OPPLUS” stands for OPERAS-PLUS; “producer” is the organization relevant for the creation of the file; “subject” relates to the overall topic of the file, as few words as possible connected with underscores or dashes; version number should indicate the version of the document (v01, v02, v03, etc.); and the dissemination level should distinguish between public (pu) and confidential (co). An example, using this file, is: OPPLUS1.2-MWS-data-management-plan-v01-pu. All files, whenever applicable, should have a versioning table.

All OPERAS-PLUS outputs deposited into the Zenodo repository will receive search keywords to optimize possibilities for re-use. OPERAS-PLUS is not using a controlled vocabulary for keywords.

All metadata will be collected and provided following the Dublin Core metadata standards, according to the Zenodo metadata schema, see <https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>.

B. Making data openly accessible

OPERAS PLUS will act according to the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” for all its generated data. Project management data and research data will be shared as early as possible. Exceptions include data containing sensitive information on the partners involved and data which are indicated as confidential (CO) in the grant agreement.

All data will be made publicly accessible as early as possible on Zenodo within the dedicated OPERAS community¹¹ and on other relevant repositories, e.g. GitHub. The Zenodo repository can process any type of file, provides an automatic DOI identifier, allows for OAI-PMH harvesting, provides 50 GB upload space, and supports flexible licensing.

¹¹ OPERAS Zenodo community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/operaseu/?page=1&size=20>.

All OPERAS-PLUS data can be accessed with standard and open source software. Documentation about the software needed to access the data is not needed. There are no restrictions on use of data, no data access committee is needed, and persons accessing the data don't need to be identified.

C. Making data interoperable

OPERAS-PLUS will follow the Semantic Publishing and Referencing Ontologies (SPAR Ontologies). The project results will use, whenever appropriate, the following standard vocabularies: Component MetaData Infrastructure (CMDI), Dublin Core Metadata Element Set and DCMI Metadata Terms. Metadata records published in RDF will use linked open data vocabularies, in particular the Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT), Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL), and DDI-RDF Discovery Vocabulary (Disco).

D. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)

All OPERAS-PLUS outputs will use Creative Commons licenses, particularly the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC-BY) or the Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0). Alternatively, outputs will use a license with equivalent rights, following the principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary".

There will be no embargoes on any data produced within the OPERAS-PLUS project and data will be made publicly available as soon as possible.

Data produced and/or used in the project, whenever publicly available and not restricted for privacy issues (see above) will be usable by third parties during and after the end of the project.

All information and processes needed to understand the applied principles of data collection will be documented. Technical specifications and documentation for outputs such as services and tools will be made publicly available on Zenodo and other relevant repositories, e.g. GitHub.

IV. Allocation of Resources

All costs associated with making data FAIR are covered by the full-time equivalent provisions of the OPERAS-PLUS project.

Responsible for data management communication is Michael Kaiser (Project Coordinator): kaiser@maxweberstiftung.de.

Responsible for the data management is Sy Holsinger (OPERAS Chief Technology Officer): sy.holsinger@operas-eu.org.

In order to ensure future access and long-term preservation, all formats and metadata will adhere to widely-recognized and utilized open standards. In particular, Zenodo is harvestable via the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH). This low-barrier mechanism for repository interoperability ensures that metadata is accessible even when the digital object is no longer there. All non-personal data will be saved as backup on the project Google shared drive. The files final versions will also be saved on the dedicated servers of the Max Weber Stiftung.

V. Data Security

All OPERAS-PLUS project partners involved in generating or collecting data for the project are responsible for a secure recovery, storage, and transfer of data - both personal and non-personal data included. The project coordination team supports partners with specific information about procedures and general regulation if needed.

VI. Ethical Aspects

The project does not implement activities or result with any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing. Particularly, it does not process or generate "EU-classified information". User research data does include personal data, and best practices for protecting participant data in user research will be followed, including informed consent and data anonymization.

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